

Rapid Communication**First record of the non-indigenous *Myrianida pachycera* (Augener, 1913) (Annelida: Syllidae) in the Mediterranean Sea revealed by integrative taxonomy**

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OPEN ACCESS**Abstract**

The non-indigenous syllid polychaete *Myrianida pachycera* (Augener, 1913), originally described from Australia, is reported for the first time in the Mediterranean Sea, based on individuals sampled in port environments in the Tyrrhenian and Ionian Sea. The identity of the specimens was investigated through morphological identification and DNA barcoding of two individuals, resulting in COI sequences with almost 100% identity with an individual from California. *Myrianida pachycera* must be considered non-indigenous for the Mediterranean Sea. The distribution of this species seems to be relatively wide in the basin, but its detection has possibly been hindered by the loss of the majority of the diagnostic characters following fixation. Conversely, due to their striking live colour pattern, live individuals might be successfully tracked via citizen science.

Key words: Polychaeta, NIS, biological invasion, Sicily, Tyrrhenian Sea, Ionian Sea

Introduction

Non-Indigenous species (NIS) are known for their impacts on native communities and human activities, representing one of the major threats to marine biodiversity worldwide (Pimentel et al. 2001; Wittenberg and Cock 2001; Mooney 2005; Vilá et al. 2010). In recent years new records of NIS in the Mediterranean Sea have been published with high frequency (Golani et al. 2013; Marchini et al. 2015; Zenetos et al. 2017), resulting in a 40% increase of established species reports since 2010 (Zenetos et al. 2022). These periodical reports are essential to understand range shifts and invasion dynamics of NIS through space and time, and inform regional conservation planning and mitigation actions (Mačić et al. 2018; Giakoumi et al. 2019). However, most research on NIS traditionally focused on fishes, molluscs, and crustaceans, while several other taxa have been neglected or scarcely studied, resulting in unfilled gaps in NIS distribution knowledge.

Marine annelids are particularly affected by uncertainties regarding their taxonomy, origin and distribution. In 2010, 130 NIS annelid species were reported in the Mediterranean Sea (Zenetos et al. 2010), even though a sizable part of them was considered questionable (Zenetos et al. 2010; Çinar 2013; Langeneck et al. 2020). Moreover, a few records derived from misidentifications of other annelid species, either already described or still undescribed ones (Del Pasqua et al. 2018; Lezzi and Giangrande 2018; Çinar and Erdoğan-Dereli 2023). Often based on taxonomic revisions, additional marine NIS annelids were reported after 2010 (Langeneck et al. 2020; Dağlı and Çinar 2022; Rousou et al. 2023; Sala-Mirete et al. 2023; Toso et al. 2024), increasing their total approximate number in the Mediterranean Sea up to around 160 species.

The amount of NIS annelid taxa reported across different areas of the Mediterranean Sea is highly variable. This is partially due to a pronounced “author effect”, i.e. an uneven distribution of annelid specialists (Giangrande and Licciano 2004; Musco and Giangrande 2005), delivering much information in countries with strong taxonomic background on annelids, such as Italy and Türkiye (Castelli et al. 1987; Tempesti et al. 2020a), while creating apparent knowledge gaps in regions where annelids are less frequently studied. Nonetheless, there is also a clear biogeographical effect, with Eastern Mediterranean countries hosting a higher number of NIS and a higher proportion of thermophilic species with Indo-Pacific affinity due to their proximity to the Suez Canal (Rousou et al. 2023). However, in recent years several NIS established in the eastern part of the basin showed clues of expansion towards the central and western Mediterranean Sea (Langeneck et al. 2020; Palero et al. 2020; Bonifazi et al. 2023; Langeneck et al. 2024a). In this context, Italy represents a geographical crossroad among different Mediterranean subregions. Its geographic position and taxonomic background contributed to make Italy the Mediterranean country with the highest number of marine NIS annelid species reported. In fact, Langeneck et al. (2020) reported overall 68 annelid NIS, and another 10 species were recently added (Gravina et al. 2021; Bonifazi et al. 2023; Borghese et al. 2023; Langeneck et al. 2024a, b), even though questionable taxa represent more than half of the reported annelid NIS (42 out of 78) stressing the need for additional taxonomic studies on this group.

Syllidae, the most species-rich annelid family, is characterised by widespread occurrence of cryptic and pseudocryptic species (Álvarez-Campos et al. 2017a, b; Aguado et al. 2019; Del Olmo et al. 2024), leading to frequent uncertainties surrounding the identity and origin of NIS (Çinar 2013; Langeneck et al. 2020). Within this family, the subfamily Autolytinae is probably the most complex from a taxonomic point of view, showing a high degree of cryptic diversity, dramatic morphological divergence between vegetative (atoke) and reproductive (epitoke) forms, and few reliable taxonomic characters (Nygren and Sundberg 2003; Nygren 2004). In fact, while in the

majority of Syllidae the shape of chaetae, antennae and dorsal cirri are often employed as diagnostic characters, they are less useful for the identification of Autolytinae. Species distinction is instead mostly based on live colour pattern, pharyngeal armature (trepan) and the presence and position of ciliary bands, which are generally difficult to examine in fixed material (Nygren and Gidholm 2001; Nygren 2004). As a consequence, the specific diversity of this subfamily is generally scarcely known, and the contribution of these species to biological invasions is generally overlooked. To date, no Autolytinae are reported as NIS in the Mediterranean Sea, and only two species, namely *Myrianida pachycera* (Augener, 1913) and *Proceraea* cf. *rubroproventriculata* Nygren and Gidholm, 2001, have been cited as possible invaders worldwide (Cohen et al. 2005; Carlton and Eldredge 2009; Keppel et al. 2019).

Another important gap of knowledge in the study of non-indigenous marine annelids is represented by the lack of molecular data, and in particular DNA barcoding sequences based on mitochondrial markers. So far, these are available only for approximately 30% of the annelid NIS reported in European waters (Lavrador et al. 2023). The lack of molecular data is worsening the taxonomic uncertainties surrounding several annelid species and has indirect negative consequences such as the impairment of environmental DNA monitoring (Maggio et al. 2023; Mugnai et al. 2023). At the same time, a significant part of the annelid sequences deposited in public repositories are identified only to the family, class or even phylum level (Langeneck et al. 2024; Toso et al. 2024), stressing the need for detailed taxonomic studies integrating morphological and molecular data. At present, DNA barcoding was carried out only on a few NIS annelids in the Mediterranean Sea (Del Pasqua et al. 2018; Grosse et al. 2021; Sala-Mirete et al. 2023; Langeneck et al. 2024a), therefore limiting our ability to trace NIS invasions in the area.

Here we report the occurrence of the Indo-Pacific annelid *Myrianida pachycera* in the Mediterranean Sea, backing the morphological identification with the mitochondrial cytochrome oxidase I gene (COI) barcoding data, and discuss its geographic distribution within the basin.

Materials and methods

Fouling assemblages were sampled by scraping artificial substrates in the harbours of Palermo, Trapani, Siracusa, Augusta and Livorno; individuals of *M. pachycera* were sorted alive, photographed and fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde in seawater or 96% ethanol for further morphological and genetic analyses. Macro photographs were obtained using a Sony ILCA-68 camera equipped with a SubSee +10 magnifier lens. Microphotographs and measurements were performed in the BioForIU Laboratory of the Salento University using a stereomicroscope SMZ 25 equipped with DS-Ri2 video camera and a video-interactive image analysis system NIS-Elements BR 4.30.02 Nikon Instruments

software. For the examination of smaller details and internal anatomy, permanent slides were obtained staining the dissected structures with Rose Bengal and mounting the slides with Faure's medium (Faure 1910). Drawings of chaetae were obtained with a Leica DM 2000 microscope equipped with a camera lucida and improved with Gimp 2.10 following the guidelines in Montesanto (2015). The examined specimens were deposited in the polychaete collections of the Museum of Marine Biology "Pietro Parenzan" of the University of Salento (PCZL) and of the Museum of Natural History of the University of Pisa (MSNP).

Genetic characterisation was carried out on two individuals of *M. pachycera*, as well as one individual of *Myrianida rubropunctata* (Grube, 1860) and one of *Amblyosyllis lineata* Grube, 1863 for comparison purposes. Total genomic DNA was extracted from a couple of posterior chaetigers using the salting-out protocol (Aljanabi and Martínez 1997) modified according to Furfaro et al. (2022). Folmer's fragment of the gene coding for the cytochrome *c* oxidase (COI) was amplified using the annelid-specific primers POLYLCO (5'-GAYTATWTTCAACAAATCATAAAGATATTGG-3') and POLYHCO (5'-TAMACTTCWGGGTGACCAAARAATCA-3') (Carr et al. 2011), using the following PCR protocol: initial denaturing step at 94 °C for 5 min, 40 cycles of denaturing at 94 °C for 45 s, annealing at 45 °C for 45 s, and extending at 72 °C for 1 min, with a final extending step at 72 °C for 7 min. A negative control was included in each reaction. The PCR products were sent to Macrogen Europe for purification and sequencing.

Phylogenetic analyses were performed using the COI sequences of *M. pachycera* available on public repositories, as well as sequences of other Autolytinae, using *Amblyosyllis spectabilis* (Johnston in Baird, 1861) and *Amblyosyllis lineata* to root the tree. DNA sequences were aligned with ClustalX v. 2.1 (Larkin et al. 2007), and alignments were edited using the program BIOEDIT v. 7.2.5 (Hall 1999). The program jModelTest 2.1.6 (Guindon and Gascuel 2003; Darriba et al. 2012) was used to assess the best model of evolution for the sequences under the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) (Akaike 1974). For all markers and genera, the most suitable substitution model was the generalised time reversible (GTR, Tavaré 1986) +I +G. A Bayesian consensus phylogenetic tree was constructed using MrBayes 3.2 (Ronquist et al. 2011). Four replicate runs were carried out with three Markov chains per run for 1×10^6 generations. The chain was sampled every 1,000 generations to obtain 2,000 sampled trees. The first 500 sampled trees (25%) were discarded as burn-in, with the remaining 1,500 trees used to estimate the Bayesian consensus, posterior probability (PP) of tree nodes. The convergence of Bayesian analyses was checked through the standard deviation of split frequencies, which should reach a value < 0.01 at the end of the analysis (Ronquist et al. 2011).

Results

Myrianida pachycera (Augener, 1913)

?*Autolytus orientalis* Willey 1905: 270, pl. 4, figs. 81, 84.

?*Autolytus maculata* Potts 1911: 36–37.

Autolytus pachycerus Augener 1913: 257–260, pl. 2, figs. 11, 12, textfig. 40A–C; 1927: 157–158.

Myrianida pachycera Imajima 1966: 79–82, fig. 26A–L; 1967: 417; Nygren 2004: 143–146, fig. 71A–E; Keppel et al. 2019: 61.

Myrianida pachycerus Hartman 1966a: 362–363, fig. 1A–B.

Autolytus purpureimaculata Okada 1933: 332–338, figs. 6–11; Imajima and Hartman 1964: 100.

Myrianida crassicirrata Hartmann-Schröder 1965: 119–121, figs. 47–49; Hartman 1966b: 194–195.

Material examined. Livorno, touristic port (43°32'54.74"N, 10°17'49.6"E), 1 m, fouling assemblages on concrete piers, 10 December 2024: 4 atoke individuals, one of them with developing stolon (MSNP: P/5224). Palermo, touristic marina (38°07'12.7"N, 13°22'01.8"E), 0.5 m, fouling assemblages on artificial substrate (concrete piers), 22 September 2023: 1 immature stolon (PCZL.SY.M.5.1). Palermo, touristic marina (38°07'10.0"N, 13°22'07.3"E), 1 m, same environment, 15 March 2024: 1 atoke individual with developing stolons (PCZL.SY.M.5.2). Palermo, touristic marina (38°07'10.0"N, 13°22'07.3"E), 1 m, same environment, 8 October 2024: 1 atoke individual with developing stolons (PCZL.SY.M.5.3), 1 detached epigamic stolon (PCZL.SY.M.5.4). Trapani, fishing port (38°00'55.4"N, 12°29'56.0"E), same environment, 11 October 2024: 1 atoke individual with developing stolons (PCZL.SY.M.5.5). Siracusa touristic marina (37°3'43.38"N, 15°17'21.37"E), 0.5 m, same environment, 29 October 2024: 1 atoke individual with developing stolons (PCZL.SY.M.5.6). Augusta, Cozzo Pisone saltern (37°14'48.52"N, 15°12'56.81"E), 0.5 m, fouling assemblages on artificial substrates, 07 November 2024: 3 atoke individuals with developing stolons (PCZL.SY.M.5.7; PCZL.SY.M.5.8; PCZL.SY.M.5.9).

Description

Body measurement and color. Largest complete individual 8.04 mm long, 1.13 mm maximum width, 50 chaetigers; longest individual 12.31 mm long, 0.51 mm maximum width, 118 chaetigers. Stock with 27–30 chaetigers, developing chain of stolons formed by up to 89 segments. Live individuals slightly flattened (Figure 1A) with two visible ciliary bands per segment, individuals after preservation in ethanol contracted, cylindrical (Figure 1B). Live colour yellowish, with a longitudinal orange stripe along each side and 5–8 transverse orange bands occurring every 2–4 chaetigers, varying between different specimens, rarely sequential over consecutive chaetigers; prostomium and peristomium dark blue, palps whitish, an unpaired dark blue triangular spot on the back of each segment starting from the 4th chaetiger. Colour pattern almost completely lost in ethanol-preserved individuals, with traces of blue pigmentation on the dorsal cirri and unpaired dark dorsal spots.

Head. Prostomium rectangular, wider than long. Two pairs of large, dark red to black eyes of similar size, inserted dorso-laterally, lateral pairs coalescent (Figure 1C). Palps short, fused, approximately as long as the

Figure 1. *Myrianida pachycera* (Augener 1913): A) Atoke individual with stolon chain from Augusta, Sicily, live; B) Atoke specimen preserved in ethanol; C) Close-up on the anterior segments; D) Detached epigamic stolon from the port of Palermo. Photographs A, C, D by Yann Toso, photograph B by Joachim Langeneck.

prostomium. Nuchal epaulettes as grooves, reaching the 4th chaetiger. Antennae, dorsal cirri and tentacular cirri club-shaped and slightly flattened, smooth but with irregular constrictions along their length. Median antenna reaching chaetiger 5–6 backwards, lateral antennae slightly thinner, approximately 3/4 the length of the median antenna. Dorsal tentacular cirri as long as median antenna, ventral tentacular cirri approximately 2/5 of dorsal tentacular cirri. Pharynx over 6 segments with one sinuation, trepan with 36 denticles, irregularly alternating between large and small ones (one larger denticle every 2–5 small ones) (Figure 2A), proventricle over 3 segments with 27 muscle cell rows.

Parapodia. All chaetigers uniramous and similar throughout the body. Parapodia with dorsal cirri around 2/3 of the length of the median antenna, approximately maintaining the same length throughout the whole body length. Dorsal cirri showing a slight alternation in size and colour, with thicker, slightly longer, blue cirrostyles in chaetigers 3, 5, 8, 10 and following even chaetigers, thinner, slightly shorter, whitish cirrostyles in chaetigers 1, 2, 4, 6, 7, 9 and following odd chaetigers. Cirrophores approximately as long

Figure 2. *Myrianida pachycera* (Augener 1913): A) Dissected trepan; B) Compound chaetae respectively (left to right) from the 5th, 5th, 22nd chaetiger from the stock, with the last one from the 2nd stolon; C) Bayonet chaetae respectively (left to right) from the 20th, 22nd chaetiger, with the last two from the 2nd stolon. Photograph by Yann Toso, drawing by Matteo Putignano.

as the parapodium, of the same length between cirri with long and short cirrostyle, slightly thinner in the latter. Ventral cirri pillow-shaped, massive, fused to the parapodium.

Chaetae. Parapodia supported by up to 3 aciculae, number of chaetae increasing towards the midbody, anteriorly with around 20 compound chaetae without dorso-ventral gradation in size of blades, in the midbody with up to 34 compound chaetae. Compound chaetae heterogomph, with short, strongly bidentate blade, secondary tooth distinctly larger than the primary one, with serrated ventral edge (Figure 2B). Bayonet chaetae (Figure 2C) present from chaetiger 11 in some specimens, starting at the end of the stock or even already in the stolon in other individuals.

Stolons and pygidium. Stolon chain with 7–33 developing stolons. Unripe stolons with smaller chaetigers, devoid of chaetae, gradually increasing in size and number of chaetae towards the pygidium. Ripe stolon with 33 chaetigers, flattened, with eyes larger than those of the atoke form, with parapodia provided with a small number of compound chaetae, one bayonet chaeta, and several natatory chaetae. Posterior chaetigers very short and numerous, pygidium with two long, thick anal cirri.

Molecular data. COI sequences were obtained for two individuals from Palermo (PCZL SY.M.5.1 and SY.M.5.2, GenBank accession numbers: PQ135964–PQ135965), both sequences showing a 99.8% identity with a

Figure 3. Bayesian phylogenetic tree of selected species of the genus *Myrianida* based on COI sequences. *Amblyosyllis lineata* and *A. spectabilis* are used as outgroup. Node values represent Bayesian posterior probabilities, sequences in bold were obtained in the present study.

deposited sequence of *M. pachycera* from California (GenBank accession number: GQ856198; Nygren et al. 2010) as well as private sequences of the same species on BOLD (Figure 3).

Remarks. The examined individuals match well the redescription by Nygren (2004), who stressed the distinctive colour pattern of this species as one of the diagnostic characters for *M. pachycera*. The only differences we identified between our material and Nygren's (2004) redescription are represented by the number of compound chaetae (up to 34 vs up to 25) and the starting point of bayonet chaetae (from chaetiger 11 vs from chaetiger 24), suggesting that these characters are subject to a higher degree of variation. All other characters, including the pharyngeal and proventricular traits, show instead a very good correspondence. Augener (1913) described *Autolytus pachycerus* from Western Australia; Imajima (1966) transferred the species to the genus *Myrianida*, proposing *Autolytus purpureimaculata* Okada, 1933 (described from Japan) as a junior synonym. Later on, Nygren (2004) confirmed the synonymy with this last taxon and suggested a further synonymy with *Myrianida crassicirrata* Hartmann-Schröder, 1965 (described from the Hawaii Islands), suggesting that *M. pachycera* has a wide distribution in the tropical and sub-tropical Pacific Ocean. Molecular and morphological data confirm that Mediterranean specimens assayed in this study belong to *M. pachycera*, as shown by the close match to a specimen from California (Nygren et al. 2010).

Discussion

Myrianida pachycera is a tropical and sub-tropical species, currently known with some certainty mainly from the Indo-Pacific region, where it was reported from Australia (Augener 1913), Japan (Imajima 1966), south China Sea (Huang 2001), the Seychelles (Böggemann et al. 2003), the Hawaii Islands (Nygren 2004), California (Nygren 2004; Cohen et al. 2005), Pacific Mexico (Tovar-Hernández et al. 2014), and the Galapagos Islands (Keppel

et al. 2019). Nygren (2004) suggested that *Autolytus orientalis*, described by Willey (1905) for Ceylon and *Autolytus maculata* described by Potts (1911) from an unknown locality might be synonymous with *M. pachycera*, but the descriptions are too scanty to confirm this hypothesis. Outside the Indian and Pacific Oceans, *M. pachycera* is currently known from Florida only (Nygren 2004). Nygren (2004) suggested that the wide distribution of *M. pachycera* might be due to anthropogenic introduction in a sizable part of its range. The absence of historical records, as well as the high sequence identity with the individual of *M. pachycera* from California, confirm that this species is a recent introduction in the Mediterranean Sea.

Interestingly, the distribution of *M. pachycera* in Italian waters seems to be rather fragmented, as the species was not detected in previous, detailed surveys of port environments focusing on non-indigenous species both in the northern Tyrrhenian Sea and along the Apulia coastline (Tamburini et al. 2021; Tempesti et al. 2022; Langeneck et al. 2024a). Recently, we were informed that a single specimen of *M. pachycera* was found in the Venice lagoon in 2016 (E. Keppel *unpublished obs.*). Still, no published data is available from 2016 to date, which suggests that a reproductive population of *M. pachycera* was never established in the Northern Adriatic after that unpublished record. In the case of the Italian harbours investigated, the subsequent finding of reproductive stages suggests the occurrence of stable, although probably small populations in the northern and southern Tyrrhenian Sea, as well as in the western Ionian Sea. While Sicilian harbours are comparatively poorly studied, and the species could have been present and undetected for several years, the port of Livorno has been continuously monitored from 2019 onwards (Tempesti et al. 2020b).

Considering that *M. pachycera* has only been found inside ports and marinas in the Mediterranean Sea, its dispersal is probably strictly navigation-mediated within the basin, and the establishment of reproductive populations and their spread northwards is probably fostered by the recent increase in surface temperatures. However, it is likely that the distribution of *M. pachycera* in the Mediterranean Sea is wider than the current data would suggest. In fact, a recent video focusing on marine worms from Antalya, Türkiye uploaded on YouTube for dissemination purposes, (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7Z-dIFZ9dCA>) shows several good-quality frames of a live specimen having the characteristic live colour pattern of *M. pachycera*. The species might also occur in the Aegean and the Levantine Sea; however, surveys of living specimens in port environments of this areas coupled with molecular analyses would be desirable to ascertain its presence.

Analysing living specimens is often crucial for the correct identification of many annelid species, but this kind of observations are seldom carried out. The spread of *M. pachycera* in the Mediterranean Sea may be underrated due to the limited number of studies focusing on living specimens. In fact, this species is as easily recognisable when alive, as poorly characterizable

when fixed. Based on our observations, direct fixation in ethanol causes a general shrinkage of the organism, and a deformation of the appendages, as well as the complete loss of the colour pattern, which ultimately leads to the impossibility to use the key provided by Nygren (2004) which is mostly based on live colour. Conversely, the unique contrasted and colourful pattern of this species makes it a popular subject for underwater photographers (http://www.flickrriver.com/photos/top_down/9429696118/; <http://www.nikon-smallworld.com/galleries/entry/2003-photomicrography-competition/2>; Fofonoff et al. 2018) suggesting that the distribution and spread of this species could be reconstructed and monitored through citizen science, either through underwater photography contests, or through the organisation of events involving citizen scientists, such as BioBlitzs (Matassa and Hitchcock 2021; Innocenti et al. 2022). This approach was successfully used for cryptobenthic marine vertebrates (Colombo and Langeneck 2013; Ragkousis et al. 2021) and invertebrates (Trainito and Doneddu 2014; Rothman et al. 2017; Langeneck et al. 2022) and, albeit seldom employed for the study of marine annelids (but see Righi et al. 2020; Langeneck et al. 2022; Fourreau et al. 2024), may help to depict the actual distribution of *M. pachycera* in the Mediterranean Sea.

Authors' contribution

Research conceptualization JL, YT, LM; sample design and methodology JL, YT, LM, MGP, SP; investigation and data collection JL, YT, AC, JT, AT; data analysis and interpretation JL, YT, LM, MP; funding provision LM, MGP, SP; writing – original draft JL, YT; writing – review and editing LM, MGP, SP, AC, MP, JT, AT.

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Data availability

Species georeferenced records are available at the European Alien Species Information Network: <https://easin.jrc.ec.europa.eu/easin/RJD/Download/c0d4ae33-fbc7-4895-8cfa4af986b5fe7>.

References

- Aguado MT, Capa M, Lago-Barcia D, Gil J, Pleijel F, Nygren A (2019) Species delimitation in *Amblyosyllis* (Annelida, Syllidae). *PLoS ONE* 14: e0214211, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0214211>
- Akaike H (1974) A new look at the statistical model identification. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control* 19: 716–723, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAC.1974.1100705>
- Álvarez-Campos P, Giribet G, Riesgo A (2017a) The *Syllis gracilis* species complex: A molecular approach to a difficult taxonomic problem. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 109: 138–150, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2016.12.036>
- Álvarez-Campos P, Giribet G, San Martín G, Rouse GW, Riesgo A (2017b) Straightening the striped chaos: systematics and evolution of *Trypanosyllis* and the case of its pseudocryptic species *Trypanosyllis krohnii* (Annelida, Syllidae). *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society* 179: 492–540, <https://doi.org/10.1111/zoj.12443>
- Aljanabi SM, Martínez I (1997) Universal and rapid salt-extraction of high quality genomic DNA for PCR-based techniques. *Nucleic Acid Research* 25: 4692–4693, <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/25.22.4692>
- Augener H (1913) Polychaeta 1, Errantia. In: Michaelsen W, Hartmeyer R (eds), Die Fauna Südwest-Australiens. Ergebnisse der Hamburger südwest-australischen Forschungsreise 1905, vol 4, Lieferung 5. Gustav Fischer, Jena, pp 65–304
- Augener H (1927) Polychaeten von Südost- und Süd-Australien. *Videnskabelige Meddelelser fra Dansk naturhistorisk Forening i København* 83: 71–275
- Böggemann M, Hessling R, Westheide W (2003) Horizontal distribution of the syllid fauna (Annelida: Polychaeta) in the fringing reef lagoon of Anse Forbans (Mahe, Seychelles) and redescription of the abundant *Streptosyllis aequiseta*. *Hydrobiologia* 496: 17–26, <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1026159823756>
- Bonifazi A, Lombardo MF, De Bonis S, Caprioli R, Fustolo M, Morgana S, Pierdomenico M, Mancini E (2023) First record of the alien and invasive polychaete *Laonome triangularis* Hutchings and Murray, 1984 (Annelida, Sabellidae) in Italian waters. *Diversity* 15: 771, <https://doi.org/10.3390/d15060771>
- Borghese J, Musco L, Arduini D, Tamburello L, Del Pasqua M, Giangrande A (2023) A comparative approach to detect macrobenthic response to the conversion of an inshore mariculture plant into an IMTA system in the Mar Grande of Taranto (Mediterranean Sea, Italy). *Water* 15: 68, <https://doi.org/10.3390/w15010068>
- Carlton JT, Eldredge LG (2009) Marine bioinvasions of Hawai'i: the introduced and cryptogenic marine and estuarine animals and plants of the Hawaiian archipelago. *Bishop Museum Bulletins in Cultural and Environmental Studies* 4: 1–202
- Carr CM, Hardy SM, Brown TM, Macdonald TA, Hebert PD (2011) A tri-oceanic perspective: DNA barcoding reveals geographic structure and cryptic diversity in Canadian polychaetes. *PLoS ONE* 6: e22232, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0022232>
- Castelli A, Gambi MC, Bianchi CN (1987) Censimento dei policheti dei mari italiani: criteri generali. *Atti della Società Toscana di Scienze Naturali, Memorie, Serie B* 94: 313–318
- Çinar ME (2013) Alien polychaete species worldwide: current status and their impacts. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the U.K.* 93: 1257–1278, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0025315412001646>
- Çinar ME, Erdoğan-Dereli D (2023) Polychaetes (Annelida: Polychaeta) off Kızılköy (Black Sea, Türkiye) with descriptions of three new species. *Zootaxa* 5383: 537–560, <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5383.4.6>
- Cohen AN, Harris LH, Bingham BL, Carlton JT, Chapman JW, Lambert CC, Lambert G, Ljubenkov JC, Murray SN, Rao LC, Reardon K, Schwindt E (2005) Rapid assessment survey for exotic organisms in southern California bays and harbors, and abundance in port and non-port areas. *Biological Invasions* 7: 995–1002, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-004-3121-1>
- Colombo M, Langeneck J (2013) The importance of underwater photography in detecting cryptobenthic species: new in situ records of some gobies (Teleostei: Gobiidae) from Italian Seas with ecological notes. *Acta Adriatica* 54: 101–110
- Dağlı E, Çinar ME (2022) A new alien polychaete species for the Mediterranean Sea: *Glycera cinnamomea* (Annelida: Glyceridae). *Mediterranean Marine Science* 23: 599–603, <https://doi.org/10.12681/mms.29867>
- Darriba D, Taboada GL, Doallo R, Posada D (2012) jModelTest 2: more models, new heuristics and parallel computing. *Nature Methods* 9: 772, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.2109>
- Del Olmo I, Roma-Cavagliani J, Martín-Hervás MdR, Langeneck J, Cervera JL, Álvarez-Campos P (2024) Integrative taxonomy in *Syllis prolifera* (Annelida, Syllidae): from a unique cosmopolitan species to a complex of pseudocryptic species. *Invertebrate Systematics* 38: IS24004, <https://doi.org/10.1071/IS24004>
- Del Pasqua M, Schulze A, Tovar-Hernández MA, Keppel E, Lezzi M, Gambi MC, Giangrande A (2018) Clarifying the taxonomic status of the alien species *Branchiomma bairdi* and *Branchiomma boholense* (Annelida: Sabellidae) using molecular and morphological evidence. *PLoS ONE* 13: e0197104, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0197104>

- Faure G (1910) Liquido conservatore per frammenti di organi e per piccoli organismi interi. *Annali di Botanica* 8: 63–64
- Fourreau CJL, Macrina L, Lalas JAA, Takahata A, Koido T, Reimer JD (2024) The Trojan seahorse: citizen science pictures of a seahorse harbour insights into the distribution and behaviour of a long-overlooked polychaete worm. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B* 291: 20241780, <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2024.1780>
- Furfaro G, Schreier C, Trainito E, Pontes M, Madrenas E, Girard P, Mariottini P (2022) The sea slug *Doriopsilla areolata* Bergh, 1880 (Mollusca, Gastropoda) in the Mediterranean Sea: Another case of cryptic diversity. *Diversity* 14: 297, <https://doi.org/10.3390/d14040297>
- Giakoumi S, Katsanevakis S, Albano PG, Azzurro E, Cardoso AC, Cebrian E, Deidun A, Edelist D, Francour P, Jimenez C, Mačić V, Occhipinti-Ambrogi A, Rilov G, Ramzi Sghaier Y (2019) Management priorities for marine invasive species. *Science of the Total Environment* 688: 976–982, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.06.282>
- Giangrande A, Licciano M (2004) Factors influencing latitudinal pattern of biodiversity: an example using Sabellidae (Annelida, Polychaeta). *Biodiversity and Conservation* 13: 1633–1646, <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:BIOC.0000029327.63397.6b>
- Golani D, Orsi-Relini L, Massuti E, Quignard J-P, Dulčić J, Azzurro E (2013) CIESM Atlas of exotic species in the Mediterranean. Vol. 1. Fishes. CIESM Publications, Monaco, 256 pp
- Gravina MF, Pierri C, Mercurio M, Nonnis Marzano C, Giangrande A (2021) Polychaete diversity related to different mesophotic bioconstructions along the southeastern Italian coast. *Diversity* 13: 239, <https://doi.org/10.3390/d13060239>
- Grosse M, Pérez R, Juan-Amengual M, Pons J, Capa M (2021) The elephant in the room: first record of invasive gregarious species of serpulids (Calcareous tube annelids) in Majorca (western Mediterranean). *Scientia Marina* 85: 15–28, <https://doi.org/10.3989/scimar.05062.002>
- Guindon S, Gascuel O (2003) A simple, fast and accurate method to estimate large phylogenies by maximum-likelihood. *Systematic Biology* 62: 696–704, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10635150390235520>
- Hall TA (1999) BioEdit: a user-friendly biological sequence alignment editor and analysis program for Windows 95/98/NT. *Nucleic Acid Symposium Series* 41: 95–98
- Hartman O (1966a) New records of some little known Australian polychaete annelids. *Records of the Australian Museum* 26: 361–365, <https://doi.org/10.3853/j.0067-1975.26.1966.685>
- Hartman O (1966b) Polychaetous annelids of the Hawaiian Islands. *Occasional Papers of the Bernice P. Bishop Museum* 23: 163–252
- Hartmann-Schröder G (1965) Zur Kenntnis der eulitoralen Polychaeten fauna von Hawaii, Palmyra und Samoa. *Naturwissenschaftlichen Vereins in Hamburg, Abhandlungen und Verhandlungen Supplement* 9: 81–161
- Huang Z (2001) Marine species and their distributions in China's seas. Krieger Pub Co, 599 pp
- Imajima M (1966) The Syllidae (polychaete annelids) from Japan (II) - Autolytinae. *Publications of the Seto Marine Biological Laboratory* 14: 27–83, <https://doi.org/10.5134/175422>
- Imajima M, Hartman O (1964) The polychaete annelids of Japan part 1. Allan Hancock Foundation Publications. *Occasional Paper* 26: 1–237
- Innocenti G, Cianfanelli S, Peoporini D, Stasolla G, Tanduo V, Crocetta F (2022) A BioBlitz in the Viareggio Marina Area reveals that the North American *Rhithropanopeus harrisii* (A. A. Gould, 1841) (Decapoda: Xanthoidea: Panopeidae) is spreading further in Italy. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 74: 605–610
- Keppel E, Keith I, Ruiz GM, Carlton JT (2019) New records of native and non-indigenous polychaetes (Annelida: Polychaeta) in the Galapagos Islands. *Aquatic Invasions* 14: 59–84, <https://doi.org/10.3391/ai.2019.14.1.03>
- Langeneck J, Lezzi M, Del Pasqua M, Musco L, Gambi, MC, Castelli A, Giangrande A (2020) Non-indigenous polychaetes along the coasts of Italy: a critical review. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 21: 238–275, <https://doi.org/10.12681/mms.21860>
- Langeneck J, Minasidis V, Doumpas N, Giovos I, Kaminas A, Kleitou P, Tiralongo F, Crocetta F (2022) Citizen science helps in tracking the range expansions of non-indigenous and neo-native species in Greece and Cyprus (Eastern Mediterranean Sea). *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering* 10: 256, <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse10020256>
- Langeneck J, Putignano M, Dimichele D, Giangrande A, Bilan M, Toso A, Musco L (2024a) Non-indigenous polychaetes along the Salento Peninsula: new records and first molecular data. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 25: 184–203, <https://doi.org/10.12681/mms.35851>
- Langeneck J, Bertasi F, Grossi L, Lefons F, Vani D, Verni S, Musco L, Castelli A (2024b) New records of one cryptogenic and two questionable alien species of polychaetes (Annelida) in Italian waters. *Acta Adriatica* 65: 2, <https://doi.org/10.32582/aa.65.2.3>
- Larkin MA, Blackshields G, Brown NP, Chenna R, McGettigan PA, McWilliam H, Valentin F, Wallace IM, Wilm A, Lopez R, Thompson JD, Gibson TJ, Higgins DG (2007) Clustal W and Clustal X version 2.0. *Bioinformatics* 23: 2947–2948, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btm404>
- Lavrador AS, Fontes JT, Vieira PE, Costa FO, Duarte S (2023) Compilation, revision, and annotation of DNA barcodes of marine invertebrate non-indigenous species (NIS) occurring in European coastal regions. *Diversity* 15: 174, <https://doi.org/10.3390/d15020174>

- Lezzi M, Giangrande A (2018) New species of Streblosoma (Thelepodidae, Annelida) from the Mediterranean Sea: *S. pseudocomatus* sp. nov., *S. nogueirai* sp. nov. and *S. hutchingsae* sp. nov. *Journal of Natural History* 52: 2857–2873, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00222933.2018.1556357>
- Mačić V, Albano PG, Almpantidou V, Claudet J, Corrales X, Essl F, Evagelopoulou A, Giovos I, Jimenez C, Kark S, Marković O, Mazaris AD, Ólafsdóttir GÁ, Panayotova M, Petović S, Rabitsch W, Ramdani M, Rilov G, Tricarico E, Vega Fernández T, Sini M, Trygonis V, Katsanevakis S (2018) Biological invasions in conservation planning: A global systematic review. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 5: 178, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2018.00178>
- Maggio T, Cattapan F, Falautano M, Julian D, Malinverni R, Poloni E, Sanseverino W, Todesco S, Castriota L (2023) eDNA metabarcoding analysis as tool to assess the presence of non-indigenous species (NIS): A case study in the bilge water. *Diversity* 15: 1117, <https://doi.org/10.3390/d15111117>
- Marchini A, Galil BS, Occhipinti-Ambrogi A (2015) Recommendations on standardizing lists of marine alien species: Lessons from the Mediterranean Sea. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 101: 267–273, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2015.09.054>
- Matassa CM, Hitchcock CB (2021) Bioblitz assessment of rocky intertidal biodiversity within the Boston Harbor Island national recreation area. *Northeastern Naturalist* 25: 200–234, <https://doi.org/10.1656/045.025.s908>
- Montesanto G (2015) A fast GNU method to draw accurate scientific illustrations for taxonomy. *ZooKeys* 515: 191–206, <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.515.9459>
- Mooney HA (2005) Invasive alien species: a new synthesis. Island Press, Washington, D.C., 368 pp
- Mugnai F, Costantini F, Chenuil A, Leduc M, Gutiérrez Ortega JM, Meglécz E (2023) Be positive: customized reference databases and new, local barcodes balance false taxonomic assignments in metabarcoding studies. *PeerJ* 11: e14616, <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.14616>
- Musco L, Giangrande A (2005) Mediterranean Syllidae (Annelida: Polychaeta) revisited: biogeography, diversity and species fidelity to environmental features. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 304: 143–153, <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps304143>
- Nygren A (2004) Revision of Autolytinae (Syllidae: Polychaeta). *Zootaxa* 680: 1–226, <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.680.1.1>
- Nygren A, Gidholm L (2001) Three new species of *Proceraea* (Polychaeta: Syllidae: Autolytinae) from Brazil and the United States, with a synopsis of all *Proceraea*-like taxa. *Ophelia* 54: 177–191, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00785236.2001.10409464>
- Nygren A, Sundberg P (2003) Phylogeny and evolution of reproductive modes in Autolytinae (Syllidae, Annelida). *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 29: 235–249, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1055-7903\(03\)00095-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1055-7903(03)00095-2)
- Nygren A, Sundkvist T, Mikac B, Pleijel F (2010) Two new and two poorly known autolytines (Polychaeta: Syllidae) from Madeira and the Mediterranean Sea. *Zootaxa* 2640: 35–52, <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.2640.1.3>
- Okada YK (1933) Two interesting syllids, with remarks on their asexual reproduction. *Memoirs of the College of Science, Kyoto Imperial University Series B* 8: 325–339
- Palero F, Torrado H, Perry O, Kupriyanova E, Ulmani A, Genis-Armero R, ten Hove HA, Capaccioni-Azzati R (2020) Following the Phoenician example: western Mediterranean colonization by *Spirobranchus* cf. *tetraceros* (Annelida Serpulidae). *Scientia Marina* 84: 83–92, <https://doi.org/10.3989/scimar.04976.20A>
- Pimentel D, McNair S, Janecka J, Wightman J, Simmonds C, O’Connell C, Wong E, Russel L, Zern J, Aquino T, Tsomondo T (2001) Economic and environmental threats of alien plant, animal, and microbe invasions. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment* 84: 1–20, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-8809\(00\)00178-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-8809(00)00178-X)
- Potts FA (1911) Methods of reproduction in the syllids. *Ergebnisse und Fortschritte der Zoologie* 3: 1–72
- Ragkousis M, Digenis M, Kovačić M, Katsanevakis S, Gerovasileiou V (2021) Rarely reported cryptobenthic fish in marine caves of the eastern Mediterranean Sea. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering* 9: 557, <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse9060557>
- Righi S, Prevedelli D, Simonini R (2020) Ecology, distribution and expansion of a Mediterranean native invader, the fireworm *Hermodice carunculata* (Annelida). *Mediterranean Marine Science* 21: 558–574, <https://doi.org/10.12681/mms.23117>
- Ronquist F, Teslenko M, van der Mark P, Ayres D, Darling A, Höhna S, Larget B, Liu L, Suchard MA, Huelsenbeck JP (2011) MrBayes 3.2: Efficient Bayesian phylogenetic inference and model choice across a large model space. *Systematic Biology* 61: 539–542, <https://doi.org/10.1093/sysbio/sys029>
- Rothman S B-S, Mienis HK, Galil BS (2017) Alien facelinid nudibranchs in the Eastern Mediterranean: first report of *Phidiana militaris* (Alder and Hancock, 1864) and report of *Caloria indica* (Bergh, 1896) 30 years after its previous sighting. *Bioinvasions Records* 6: 125–128, <https://doi.org/10.3391/bir.2017.6.2.06>
- Rousou M, Langeneck J, Apsperou C, Arvanitidis C, Charalambous S, Chrysanthou K, Constantinides G, Dimitriou PD, García Gómez SC, Hadjieftychiou SI, Katsiaras N, Kleitou P, Kletou D, Küpper FC, Louizidou P, Martins R, Moraitis ML, Papageorgiou N, Papatheodoulou M, Petrou A, Xevgenos D, Vasiliades L, Voultziadou E, Chintiroglou CC,

- Castelli A (2023) Polychaetes (Annelida) of Cyprus (Eastern Mediterranean Sea): An updated and annotated checklist including new distribution records. *Diversity* 15: 941, <https://doi.org/10.3390/d15080941>
- Sala-Mirete A, López E, Fernández-Álías A, Sánchez-Fernández O, Marcos C, Pérez-Ruzafa A (2023) *Leodamas australiensis* (Hartmann-Schröder, 1979) (Polychaeta, Orbiniidae), a new alien species in the Mediterranean, and its ecology in the Mar Menor coastal lagoon (SE Spain). *BioInvasions Records* 12: 993–1013, <https://doi.org/10.3391/bir.2023.12.4.13>
- Tamburini M, Keppel E, Marchini A, Repetto MF, Ruiz GM, Ferrario J, Occhipinti-Ambrogi A (2021) Monitoring non-indigenous species in port habitats: First application of a standardized north American protocol in the Mediterranean Sea. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 8: 700730, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.700730>
- Tavaré S (1986) Some probabilistic and statistical problems in the analysis of DNA sequences. *Lectures in Mathematics and Life Sciences* 17: 57–86
- Tempesti J, Mangano MC, Langeneck J, Lardicci C, Maltagliati F, Castelli A (2020a) Non-indigenous species in Mediterranean ports: A knowledge baseline. *Marine Environmental Research* 161: 105056, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marenvres.2020.105056>
- Tempesti J, Langeneck J, Maltagliati F, Castelli A (2020b) Macrobenenthic fouling assemblages and NIS success in a Mediterranean port: The role of use destination. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 150: 110768, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2019.110768>
- Tempesti J, Langeneck J, Romani L, Garrido M, Lardicci C, Maltagliati F, Castelli A (2022) Harbour type and use destination shape fouling community and non-indigenous species assemblage: A study of three northern Tyrrhenian port systems (Mediterranean Sea). *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 174: 113191, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2021.113191>
- Toso A, Putignano M, Fumarola LM, Bariche M, Giangrande A, Musco L, Piraino S, Langeneck J (2024) A revised inventory of Annelida in the Lebanese coastal waters with ten new aliens for the Mediterranean Sea. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 25: 715–731, <https://doi.org/10.12681/mms.37998>
- Tovar-Hernández MA, Yáñez-Rivera B, Villalobos-Guerrero T F, Aguilar-Camacho JM, Ramírez-Santana ID (2014) Invertebrados marinos exóticos en el Golfo de California. In: Low Pfeng AM, Quijón PA, Peters Recagno EM (eds), *Especies invasoras acuáticas: casos de estudio en ecosistemas de México*. Secretaría de Medio Ambiente y Recursos Naturales (Semarnat), Instituto Nacional de Ecología y Cambio Climático (INECC), University of Prince Edward Island (UPEI), Mexico, pp 15–32
- Trainito E, Doneddu M (2014) First record of living specimens of *Spinoaglaja wildpretii* (Gastropoda: Cephalaspidea: Aglajidae). *Marine Biodiversity Records* 7: e39, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1755267214000396>
- Vilá M, Basnou C, Pyšek P, Josefsson M, Genovesi P, Gollasch S, Nentwig W, Olenin S, Roques A, Roy D, Hulme PE, DAISIE partners (2010) How well do we understand the impacts of alien species on ecosystem services? A pan-European, cross-taxa assessment. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment* 8: 135–144, <https://doi.org/10.1890/080083>
- Willey A (1905) Report on the Polychaeta collected by Professor Herdman, at Ceylon, in 1902. *Report to the Government of Ceylon on the Pearl Oyster Fisheries of the Gulf of Mannar* 4: 243–324
- Wittenberg R, Cock MJW (eds) (2001) *Invasive alien species: a toolkit of best prevention and management practices*. CAB International, Wallingford, Oxon, UK, 228 pp, <https://doi.org/10.1079/9780851995694.0000>
- Zenetos A, Gofas S, Verlaque M, Çinar ME, García Raso J, Bianchi CN, Morri C, Azzurro E, Bilecenoglu M, Froggia C, Siokou I, Violanti D, Sfriso A, San Martín G, Giangrande A, Katağan T, Ballesteros E, Ramos-Esplá A, Mastrototaro F, Ocaña O, Zingone A, Gambi MC, Strefitaris N (2010) Alien species in the Mediterranean Sea by 2010. A contribution to the application of European Union's Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD). Part I. Spatial distribution. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 11: 381–493, <https://doi.org/10.12681/mms.87>
- Zenetos A, Çinar ME, Crocetta F, Golani D, Rosso A, Servello G, Shenkar N, Turon X, Verlaque M (2017) Uncertainties and validation of alien species catalogues: the Mediterranean as an example. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 191: 171–187, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2017.03.031>
- Zenetos A, Albano PG, Lopez Garcia E, Stern N, Tsiamis K, Galanidi M (2022) Established non-indigenous species increased by 40% in 11 years in the Mediterranean Sea. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 23: 196–212, <https://doi.org/10.12681/mms.29106>

Web sites, online databases and software

- Fofonoff PW, Ruiz GM, Steves B, Simkanin C, Carlton JT (2018) National Exotic Marine and Estuarine Species Information System. <https://invasions.si.edu/nemesis> (accessed 24 September 2024)